

A close-up photograph of a large, hairy Hersiliidae spider on a branch. The spider has a mottled pattern of brown, orange, and green on its body. A small, dark insect is perched on its back. The background is a soft-focus natural setting with green leaves and brown branches.

THE HERSILIIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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Desiré Pelsler

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ABSTRACT

The Hersiliidae, a Gondwanan distribution, is known from 16 genera and 182 species. Three genera and 12 species are recorded from South Africa of which seven are endemics. All known species were revised. Ten species are listed as Least Concern. *Tyrotama soutpansbergensis* Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005 is currently threatened by loss of habitat due to infrastructure development around Polokwane and faces a future threat of mining on the Soutpansberg. It qualifies as Vulnerable under Criterion B. *Tyrotama taris* Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005 is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons as the placement of the male is problematic and too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made.

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Hersilia sp. eye pattern Photo Vida vd Walt

FAMILY HERSILIIDAE Thorell, 1870

A family with a Gondwanan distribution. Known from 16 genera and 182 species. Three genera and 12 species are recorded from South Africa of which seven are endemics (World Spider Catalogue 2020).

COMMON NAME: Hersiliidae (long-spinnered spiders or two-tailed spiders); *Hersilia* (long-spinnered bark spiders); *Tyrotama* (long-spinnered desert spiders).

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 5-12 mm. Colour varies from golden brown to pure white to almost black with a mottled appearance. Carapace densely covered with plumose setae; ovoid and flattened with a narrow longitudinal fovea; radiating striae; eyes 8 in 2 strongly recurved rows situated on a large eye tubercle. Abdomen flat; densely covered with plumose setae; wider behind than in the front; posterior spinnerets as long as abdomen; cylindrical with elongated and tapering apical segments; inner surface of spinnerets with series of long tubules that produce thin silk threads. Legs very long, especially in males; leg III shortest in both sexes (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005a,b; 2006); (Foord 2008).

LIFE STYLE: *Hersilia* is free-running commonly found on the bark of trees where its mottled appearance makes it blend in with the surroundings. With their flattened bodies they are able to lay flat against the bark, without casting any shadows. They attack pedestrian prey by circling around them facing away, and covering it with bands of silk from their enormously elongated spinnerets. The egg cocoons are attached to the bark of the tree and camouflaged with loose bark and debris. *Neotama* and *Tama* are web dwellers making their webs under stones. They are usually found under stones where they build irregular retreat webs. The retreat consists of a circular wall of closely woven webbing plastered with small stones, chips and vegetable debris. The outside of the wall is concave and smooth while the inside is decorated with a mass of fine strands and small stone chips. Around the circular wall, the web is extended by a mass of fine trip lines attached to stones or other objects. The spider uses speed to overpower prey then carrying it immediately back to the nest. The egg cocoon is attached to the underside of the stone and covered with stone chips (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014); (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014).

TAXONOMY: The South African genera were revised by Foord (2008) and Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a, 2006).

Hersiliidae. a *Hersilia* sp., female, dorsal view; b: eye pattern, dorsal view; c: spinnerets ventral view' d. epigyne, e. male palp, ventral view; f: male palp, lateral view (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997).

GENUS *HERSILIA* Audouin, 1826

COMMON NAME: Long Spinnered Tree Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Hersilia caudata* Audouin, 1826

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL (5-10 mm). Colour varies from golden brown to pure white to almost black with a mottled appearance. Carapace densely covered with plumose setae; ovoid and flattened with a narrow longitudinal fovea and radiating striae; thoracic region the widest; fovea is longitudinal with radial striae; eyes 8 in 2 strongly recurved rows situated on a large eye tubercle; chelicerae armed with teeth on the pro- and retromargin. Abdomen longer than wide; widest in the posterior third; dorsoventrally flattened; densely covered with plumose setae; with four pairs of distinct dorsal muscular pits that vary in size; *Hersilia* is recognized by the lateral spinnerets, longer than the carapace width; posterior spinnerets as long as abdomen; cylindrical with elongated and tapering apical segments; inner surface of spinnerets with series of long tubules that produce thin silk threads. Legs very long, especially in male with leg III shortest in both sexes (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006).

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living bark dweller. Adults are found on the bark of a variety of trees, including orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014). They do not seem to prefer specific tree species, although size of tree trunk seems to play a role. Females construct flat oval-shaped egg sacs on the surface of tree trunks that is camouflaged with bits of bark. She holds guard over the eggs in an upside down position until young emerge.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006).

Hersilia sp. Photo Desiree Pelsler

H. arborea

H. sagitta

H. sericea

H. setifrons

Abdomens after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Hersilia arborea Lawrence, 1928

COMMON NAME: Long Spinnered Tree Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1928) from Namibia. It is known from three African countries. In South African the species is recorded from four provinces (EOO= 272 938 km²; AOO=32 km²; 271-1535 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to species wide range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living bark dweller. They are cryptic and remain with their bodies pressed to the substrate when at rest, moving at great speed when disturbed. They were sampled from trees by hand, from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature reserve (-25.80, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pongola (-27.35; 31.61). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.120, 30.184); Lekgalameetse, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Lephalale (-23.670, 27.746); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64). **Northern Cape:** Groblershoop (-28.88, 21.98).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Species protected in areas such as Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) and Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006). Known from both sexes.

Hersilia arborea female with egg sac from Pretoria
Photo Peter Webb

Male palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Hersilia arborea female from Pretoria Photo Les Oates

Hersilia sagitta Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006

COMMON NAME: Kenya Long Spinnered Tree Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 2006 from Kenya. It has been recorded from four African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from two provinces, including two protected area (EOO=85 804 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 93-1148 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living bark dweller. They are cryptic and remain with their bodies pressed to the substrate when at rest, moving at great speed when disturbed. They are usually found in forest areas and in South Africa sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo:* Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Kruger National Park (Pafuri Camp) (-22.46, 31.03); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Soutpansberg (-22.967, 29.40). *KwaZulu Natal:* Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from two protected areas: Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020a). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006). Known from both sexes.

Hersilia sagitta from Kruger NP Photo SANSA VM

Male palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Abdomen after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Hersilia sericea Pocock, 1898

COMMON NAME: Common Long Spinnered Tree Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1898 from Estcourt in South Africa. It is known from six African countries. In South Africa, the species is widely distributed, occurring in eight of the nine provinces including in more than 10 protected areas (EOO=852 841 km²; AOO= 240 km²; 4-1471 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to the species wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living bark dweller. Adults are found on the bark of a variety of trees, including trees in orchards. They do not seem to prefer specific tree species, although size of tree trunk seems to play a role. Females construct flat oval-shaped egg sacs on the surface of tree trunks that are camouflaged with bits of bark. She guards the eggs in an upside down position until young emerge. Females have been caught throughout the year and males from April through to December. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Had-dad et al. 2013) and also sampled from avocado, citrus, grapefruit and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013). Some specimens were collected from walls in built up areas.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Kenya, Mozambique, Swaziland, Tanzania, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebbe Nature Reserve (The Haven) (-32.28, 28.9); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane: Queenswood (-25.74, 28.19), Sinoville (-25.67, 28.23), Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). Irene Gem Village Field (-25.868, 28.218); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane Queenswood (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Chakaskraal (-29.45, 31.22); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29, 29.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), Fanie's Gate (-28.1, 32.45), Kosi Bay (-26.93, 32.87); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Krantzklouf (-29.55, 30.91); Mtunzini (-28.96, 31.76); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (4 km W) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Verulam (-29.62, 31.06); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.16, 30.37).

Hersilia sericea from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Male palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Abdomen after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Epigynum Photo ASD

Hersilia sericea from Ndumo Photo Peter Webb

Hersilia sericea (continued)

Limpopo: Alldays (-22.67, 29.1); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Farm Elandsberg, between Warmbath /Thabazimbi (-24.73, 27.72); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93 Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03; 29.45); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Kruger National Park (Olifants Camp) (-22.93, 31.02); Maasstroom (Farm Al-te-ver) (-22.75, 28.43); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Thabazimbi Shabalala (-24.6, 27.38); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29). Leggalameetse, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Medike Mountain Reserve Soutpansberg (-22.994, 29.614); Naboomspruit Rhemardo Holiday Resort (-24.52, 28.7). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (Farm De Villiers) 20 km NE (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Farm Glenwood (-25.48,30.92); Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94); Kranspoort, near Loskopdam (-25.42, 29.43); Kruger National Park (Satara) (-24.38, 31.78); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Nelspruit, Agricultural College (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit, Hall & Sons, 10 km NE (-25.47, 30.96); Schagen, 15 km NW (-25.43, 30.8). **North West:** Swartruggens (Farm Olivenkloof 373 JP) (-25.54, 26.52). **Northern Cape:** Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3,22.44). **Western Cape:** Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded in more than 10 protected areas such as Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) and Leggalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006). Known from both sexes.

Hersilia sericea from Wonderboom Photo Hannes Mitchell

Hersilia sericea from Eshowe Photo Peter Webb

Hersilia setifrons Lawrence, 1928

COMMON NAME: Namibian Long Spinnered Tree Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1928 from Namibia. It is known from three African countries. In South Africa, the species is widely distributed occurring in six of the nine provinces including nine protected areas. It occurs in the more western regions and is sympatric with *H. sericea* towards the wetter eastern parts (EOO= 779 958 km²; AOO= 84 km²; 47-1556 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living bark dweller. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane: Hazelwood (-25.78, 28.26), Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2); Bronkhorstspuit (Bashewa) (-25.8, 28.74); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Pretoria/ Tshwane Brooklyn (-25.74, 28.19); Tshwane Menlo Park (-25.74, 28.19); Tshwane Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-28.92, 31.35); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61); iSimangaliso WP Mission Rocks Picnic Site (-28.264, 32.483). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.424, 30.911); Tshulu Camp (Venda) (-22.580, 30.809); Klein Kariba (-24.50, 28.20). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman (Dithakong Tribal Land, 65 km N E) (-27.46; 23.43); Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.56, 24.162); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44). **North West:** Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded in nine protected areas such as Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006). Known from both sexes.

Hersilia setifrons female from Tswalu NR
Photo Peter Webb

Male palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Hersilia setifrons male from Tswalu NR Photo Peter Webb

GENUS NEOTAMA Baehr & Baehr, 1993

COMMON NAME: Neotama Long Spinnered Tree Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Neotama variata* (Pocock, 1899)

MORPHOLOGY: Female TL 6.3–7.1 mm. Colour of carapace pale yellow to pale brown, with brown and white spots laterally; clypeus pale, white anteriorly; eye area dark around eyes; white mark posteriad on eye tubercle; abdomen white with dark borders anteriorly; dorsally with lancet-shaped heart mark; posterior half of abdomen V-shaped, dark border around; with dorsal muscular pits; ventrum mottled white; posterior lateral spinnerets with no or faint annulation; legs pale yellow with dark brown patellae; femora and palps with faint annulation. Male total length 4.92 (4.83–5); closely resembles females except smaller body and longer legs.

LIFE STYLE: Arboreal spiders found mainly on tree trunks in forests. Adult females were collected during October and November, adult males in January and July; arboreal, caught in forest on tree trunks (Foord et al. 2011; Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005b).

TAXONOMY: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005b).

Neotama sp. from Eastern Cape Photo Linda Wiese

Neotama corticola (Lawrence, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Durban Long Spinnered Tree Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1937 as *Hersilia corticola* from Durban in KwaZulu-Natal. In South Africa, the species is recorded from three provinces, including six protected areas (EOO= 132 015 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 45-1307 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STRYLE: An arboreal free-living species found mainly on tree trunks in forest areas. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve (-32.605, 26.388); Gonjah (-33.42, 24.44). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bluff nr Durban (-29.88, 31.02); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ngoje Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57). **Western Cape:** Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005). Known from both sexes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded from six protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

Neotama corticola male Photo ASD

Male palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005b)

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005b)

Neotama corticola spinnerets after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005b)

Genus *TYROTAMA* Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005

COMMON NAME: Two-tailed ground spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Tyrotama arida* Smithers, 1945.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 4–9 mm. Colour: carapace varies from pale yellow to dark brown, bordered with intermittently darker patches; clypeus pale to dark; abdomen pale to dark brown, heart-shaped mark dark. Carapace as wide as or wider than long; fovea longitudinal with radial striae; eyes on a low tubercle; chelicerae elongate, at least twice as long as wide, unarmed; sternum heart-shaped. Abdomen oval convex; densely covered with plumose setae, with plain setae scattered in between; posterior lateral spinnerets longer than others. Leg IV longest; leg formula 4213. Males are smaller in size and with legs longer in relation to body length. *Tyrotama* differs from *Hersilia* in having shorter legs with metatarsi having only one segment.

ABUNDANCE: More abundant in drier regions.

LIFE STYLE: *Tyrotama* are found under stones where they build irregular webs. They construct a circular-retreat of closely woven webbing in which small pebbles, chips and vegetable debris are incorporated. Anchor threads attached to the substratum warn the spider of approaching prey. They move at great speed, overpowering their prey and dragging it back to their retreat where they feed on it. Prey capture resembles that of *Hersilia* in that the prey is rapidly encircled, usually in a clock-wise direction. In the process the prey is ensnared in silk emanating from the posterior lateral spinnerets. The prey is then killed with a bite to the head. Their round egg sacs are attached to the underside of a stone and covered with stone chips.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a).

Abdomens after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Tyrotama arida stone nest with egg sacs from Cederberg Photo: Norman Larsen

Tyrotama abyssus Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005

COMMON NAME: Swartberg Two-tailed ground spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2005, from Gamkaskloof in the Swartberg Nature Reserve, Western Cape. The species is also known from Lesotho. In South Africa presently known from two provinces, including five protected areas (EOO= 260 309 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 172-1706 m a.s.l.). The species is possibly under collected. There are no significant threats and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Found under stones where they build circular webs attached to the underside of the stone from which it hangs, almost like a veil. The entrance is on the northern side. Sampled from the Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Carnarvon (-30.97, 22.12); Blouyfer near Williston (-31.35, 20.92); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.814, 21.173); Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.35, 21.67).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded in six protected areas such as Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020c). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female.

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Carapace after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Habitus after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Tyrotama abyssus from Swartberg NR Photo J Hilton

Tyrotama abyssus from Aardvark NR Photo Peter Webb

Tyrotama arida (Smithers, 1945)

COMMON NAME: Cape Arid Long Spinnered Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1945 as *Tama arida* from Montagu in the Western Cape. The species is known from two provinces, including three protected areas (EOO= 534 671 km²; AOO= 56 km²; 78-1850 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Collected under flat stones on rocky areas where they build circular webs attached to the underside of the stone from which it hangs, almost like a veil. The entrance is on the northern side. A female was sampled with six egg sacs congregated in a heap, covered with small stone chips. Four of the sacs were empty, one contained hatching eggs and from the remaining one, young spiders were emerging. The species is frequently found in pitfall traps in the Fynbos, Desert, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Blouysfer near Williston (-31.35, 20.92); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Williston (-31.34, 20.92). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Matroosberg (-33.42, 9.84); Sanddrift, Dwars River (-32.16, 18.89); Touws River (-33.44, 21.18); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89). Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, 531 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area Aan Het Berg 2.3, 258m a.s.l. (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass, 551 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop 1881m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop, 1669 m a.s.l. (-32.354, 19.168); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop 1570 m a.s.l. (-32.349, 19.169); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop 1615 m a.s.l. (-32.354, 19.153); Cederberg, Sneeuokop, 1881m a.s.l. (-32.354, 19.163); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop 1557 m a.s.l. (-32.348, 19.171); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop 1597 m a.s.l. (-32.349, 19.169); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, 551m a.s.l. (-32.349, 19.006); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 531m a.s.l. (-32.280, 19.220).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded in three protected areas such as Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016) and Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a). Known from both sexes.

Abdomen and carapace and genitalia after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Tyrotama arida Photo Esther vd Westhuizen

Tyrotama arida Photo Anka Eichhoff

Tyrotama australis (Simon, 1893)

COMMON NAME: Hanover Long Spinnered Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1893 as *Hersiliola australis* from Hanover, Poortjiesfontein. The species is also recorded from Botswana and Lesotho. In South Africa, it is known in six provinces and nine protected areas (EOO= 1 064 492 km²; AOO= 144 km²; 54-1765 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is commonly found under stones where they build circular webs attached to the underside of the stone from which it hangs, almost like a veil. The entrance is on the northern side. Most specimens, especially males, in museum collections were caught in pitfall traps. Males were collected between February and April, and females between November and February. Found in the Desert, Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Tussen Die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.49, 25.99); Florisbad (-28.77, 26.08); Wolfkop (-29.13, 26.07); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Naval Hill, Hangmanskloof (-29.06, 26.14); Farm Mountain View (-29.02, 26.13); Moreson (-27.31, 29.06); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens (-29.08, 26.10); Kalkfontein, from house to dam (-29.31, 25.17). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); Pongola, farm Vergeval (-27.35, 31.61); Dawns Pride (-28.55, 29.78); Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73). **Limpopo:** Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Rochdale farm (-22.54, 29.41); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); National Park, Shingwedzi (20km SE) (-23.217, 31.567). **Mpumalanga:** Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39). **Northern Cape:** Colesberg (-30.73, 25.11); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Poortjiesfontein (-30.97, 24.45); Witsand Nature Reserve (-28.36, 23.05); Green Valley (-28.43, 21.25); Poortjiesfontein (-30.97, 24.45); Postmasburg Witsand Nature Reserve (-28.36, 23.05); Richtersveld National Park (-28.33, 17.01); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162); Cape Victoria West (-31.24, 23.07); Farm Sunnyside (-27.43, 23.36). **North West:** Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73).

Palp after Foord & Dippenaar-

Epigynum after Foord &

Tyrotama australis from Fouriesburg Photo Peter Webb

Abdomen and carapace after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Tyrotama australis (continued)

Western Cape: Ashton (-33.83, 20.06); Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Beaufort West, farm Kantkraal (-33.28, 23.22); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Montagu, Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Mossel Bay (-34.18, 22.12); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Robertson (-33.8, 19.87). Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Du Toits Kloof Pass (-33.72, 19.18); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded in nine protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a). Known from both sexes.

Tyrotama australis from Fouriesburg Photo Peter Webb

Tyrotama bicava (Smithers, 1945)

COMMON NAME: Long Spinneret Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1945 as *Tama bicava* from Namibia. It is known from three African countries. In South Africa, the species is only known from one locality in Marble Hall, Limpopo (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 895 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is found under stones where they builds circular webs attached to the underside of the stone from which it hangs, almost like a veil. The entrance is on the northern side. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Marble Hall (-25.09, 29.09).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005). Known from both sexes.

Epigynum and palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Carapace and abdomen after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Tyrotama bicava female Photo Peter Webb

Tyrotama bicava male Photo Anka Eichhoff

Tyrotama incerta (Tucker, 1920)

COMMON NAME: Nieuwoudtville Long Spinnered Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1920 as *Tama incerta* from Nieuwoudtville in the Northern Cape. It is known from two African countries and in South Africa known from two provinces including two protected areas: Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve and Karoo National Park (EOO=54 668 km²; AOO=44 km²; 83-1167m a.s.l.). Although threatened by loss of habitat for agricultural activities in parts of its the majority of its range is not threatened, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is found under stones where they build circular webs attached to the underside of the stone from which it hangs, resembling a veil. The entrance is on the northern side. They often have their retreats on the dry rocky northern and western slopes, typically where you find rock on rock. Sampled from the Nama Karoo and Fynbos biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Nieuwoudtville, Bokkeveld Mountains (-31.37, 19.11); Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve (-31.37, 19.11). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Ceres, Matroosberg (-33.36, 19.31); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Laingsburg (-33.2, 20.85); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Touws River (-33.44, 21.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: This species has lost habitat to crop cultivation on the Bokkeveld Escarpment and around Clanwilliam however the majority of its range is still natural. It is found in two protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005). Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Carapace and abdomen after Foord &

Tyrotama incerta Photo Charles Haddad

Tyrotama incerta Photo Walter Jubber

Tyrotama soutpansbergensis Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005

COMMON NAME: Soutpansberg Long Spinnered Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU

NATIONAL CRITERIA: B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described in 2005 from the Soutpansberg. It has a restricted distribution known from five locations, and protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (EOO=9 149 km²; AOO=28 km²; 710-1325 m a.s.l.). It is currently threatened by loss of habitat due to infrastructure development around Polokwane and faces a future threat of mining on the Soutpansberg. It qualifies as Vulnerable under Criterion B.

LIFE STYLE: The species is found under stones where it builds circular webs attached to the underside of the stone from which it hangs, almost like a veil. They are typically found in the hot, north facing sections of the Soutpansberg. Sampled from the Savanna biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Limpopo: Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Soutpansberg (Farm Rochdale) (-22.54, 29.41); Vhembe Biosphere Bristow Farm (-23.1670, 29.7797); Vhembe Biosphere Goro Ranch (-22.982, 29.416); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27); Abel Erasmus Pass, near Mogoba (-24.46, 30.61); Leboeng (-24.687, 30.251).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat to infrastructure development around Polokwane, there is also a future mining threat on the Northern side of the Soutpansberg. But it is protected in two reserves.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Epigynum and palp after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Carapace and abdomen after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Tyrotama soutpansbergensis female from

Habitat of the species Photo S. Foord

Tyrotama taris Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005

COMMON NAME: Richtersveld Long Spinnered Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 2005 and known only from type locality in Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park with no known threats (EEO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 346 m a.s.l.). Placement of the male is problematic and too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is commonly found under stones where it builds irregular webs. Known from the Desert Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is protected in the Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

Abdomen after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Carapace after Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2005a)

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